

The Impact of Social Media on Grassroot Level Politics in India

Erick Jamesa
Research Scholar, Amal Jyothi
College, Kanjirappally, Kerala,
(India)
erickjames4512@gmail.com

Dr. Bijimol T.K
Assoc. Professor, Dept. of Computer
Science, Amal Jyothi College,
Kanjirappally, Kerala (India),
tkbijimol@amaljyothi.ac.in

Siji Antony
Asst. Professor, Dept. of
Computer Science, Santhigiri
College, Vazhithala, Kerala
(India), sijiantony20@gmail.com

Abstract- Social media has knitted itself to the world of politics not long ago in the geopolitical areas in India. India has been going through a digital revolution in most of the parts and local politics has its fair share of benefits to. This research focus on how these social media platforms imitate the traditional election engagement into mobilizing voters, challenging the existing power structures and approaching the public. Also this research look into the misinformation and disinformation in these political campaigns and how the publics are fed these propaganda politics.

Keywords: Social Media, Grassroot Politics, Election Engagement, Political Mobilization, Misinformation, Disinformation, Digital Literacy, Political Campaigns, Civic Engagement, India, Rural Politics, Urban Politics, Community Outreach, Political Efficacy, Political Communication, Digital Revolution

I. Introduction

Indian Political landscapes are changing with the exposure to the social media as it is a double edged sword it makes a positive and negative impact. On a positive note social media can make any local election or any small electoral process go through a global spectators. People can know what other parts of the country are doing in these democratic process and It wasn't the case a decade ago. Also India is visibly the country that tends to spread false information concerning the election processes. This digital threat undermines democratic processes and destabilizes governments, so its function in the system needs to be critically examined. Simultaneously, the importance of grassroots efforts in India's electoral environment cannot be emphasized. These grassroots initiatives, which range from voter registration drives to election campaign management, are crucial to maintaining a robust and inclusive democratic process even in the face of social media's explosive impact. And it can't be neglected that only near half of the Indian public has a presence in social media.

It also commendable that social media is redefining the political campaigning as the virtual interactions between candidate and the public are far more suitable for the public and helps in micro targeting, reaching specific demographics and the cost effectiveness in these processes

II. Importance of Election awareness

The World Economic Forum's 'Global Risks Report 2024'[15] has revealed that, with its general elections coming up this year, India is most vulnerable to disinformation. The analysis emphasizes how different countries will view misinformation and disinformation as issues over the course of the next two years.

According to the paper, misinformation is the unintended spread of inaccurate information, whereas disinformation is the deliberate deception of audiences. It highlights the crucial role that these risks play during general elections, emphasizing how they could destabilize recently elected administrations and weaken democratic processes as a result of the flows, especially with the increasing use of social media platforms and the blurring line between AI- and human-generated content.

Additionally, by giving marginalized communities—such as women, youth, and ethnic minorities—access to pertinent electoral information and resources, election awareness campaigns via social media channels have the potential to empower them and give them a voice in politics. This will allow them to meaningfully participate in the electoral process. Essentially, election awareness—made possible by social media—enhances India's democratic fabric by educating, energizing, and empowering voters, which in turn fuels grassroots politics.

Social media platforms function as dynamic centers for the distribution of up-to-date information and timely reminders about voting places, voter registration deadlines, and other critical electoral details. Social media platforms successfully reach a

variety of audiences, including young voters and those who live in remote or marginalized locations, through targeted advertising campaigns, educational images, and interactive material. Election awareness campaigns are able to actively contact with people and respond to their questions by utilizing the interactive features of social media.

III. Information Access in India

India's General Election is the biggest democratic Election in the world, it involves a large group of people (near 75%) whom are aware of the presence of social medias like WhatsApp and Facebook but only near half of the population are involved in these social platforms[8]. As social media has the ability to give a wider perception on different matters it helps in the information revolving your candidate, your political party etc.

These platforms make it easier for people to engage directly with political leaders and parties, disseminate political news in real time, and participate in political conversation. Furthermore, the algorithmic features of social media allow for the personalization of content delivery, guaranteeing that users receive information that is specific to their interests and preferences. This focused strategy improves consumers' access to political information by giving them interesting and pertinent content. Additionally, social media platforms facilitate citizen journalism, which expands the range of political information sources by allowing regular people to report on political events and express their viewpoints. Social media plays a vital role in bolstering democracy in India by democratizing access to political information and encouraging more civic engagement. But issues like the dissemination of false information and echo chambers also highlight the ardent need for media literacy and critical thinking skill

Urban and rural locations differ significantly when it comes to information access. India's rural communities still lack complete digital literacy. Nevertheless, this disparity would close soon. It is impossible to overestimate the significance of social media in local elections since these platforms have become effective means of interacting with voters, rallying support, and influencing public opinion at the local level. In contrast to conventional media platforms like television and newspapers, social media gives local politicians and campaigns the chance to instantly and directly connect with their target audiences. Through the use of social media sites such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and Twitter, candidates may disseminate their messages, share their platforms, and interact with voters on issues that are most important to their communities. [9] [13]

IV. The power of social media campaigns in grassroots politics

Social media's role in general election in 2014,2019 was revolutionary in India ruling party BJP's "chai pe charcha" a video conference with the now prime minister Narendra Modi and the #mainnahihum by Indian national congress in 2019 was successful campaigns although later campaign didn't reflect it on the result[6]

The case in local level was different there are only few cases of success political campaigns in social media has been outed, one would be the case of Aam Aadmi party's electoral campaign in Delhi. To reach voters locally, the Aam Aadmi Party (AAP) used a grassroots social media approach during the Delhi Municipal Corporation elections. In order to respond to issues voiced by locals in different neighborhoods, plan community activities, and spread information about the party's candidates, AAP volunteers and supporters used Facebook groups and WhatsApp. In addition, the party organized a number of Twitter town halls and Facebook Live events where candidates engaged directly with voters, responding to their inquiries and requesting input. The AAP was able to capture a sizable number of seats in the municipal elections by connecting with people at the grassroots level thanks to its emphasis on targeted, community-driven participation through social media.[1][11]

Coming to the rural area elections Shiv sena in Maharashtra used short impactful videos for their campaign in 2019 in panchayat elections. Tamilnadu also recently undergone such digital transformation in their 2021 assembly election where DML party effectively utilized mediums like Facebook and twitter to spread their manifesto and used social media influencers to create a buzz in social media

V. Misinformation and its adverse Effects

As the political parties are more familiar with the platform nowadays it's easier to attack the opposition in the platform. Convincing lies and covered truths are common in social media that leads to misinformation. false narratives and provocative material have the power to deepen already-existing social and political divides by fostering mistrust and hostility between various communities and organizations. This may obstruct fruitful discussion and jeopardize democratic procedures, also hate speech and fake news have the power to instigate violence and discrimination against people or groups on the basis of their political beliefs, race, religion, or caste. Real-world repercussions including physical assaults, rioting, and social upheaval may result from this.

These false accusations were very common in the recent past like the fake news about the origin of the covid -19 virus, the false particular antireligion slogan raised by another religion social media handle in CAA protests which was actually a fake information[5]. These news spread in social media like fire and the common people doesn't have time to fact check what they see and hear it manipulates their

voting decision to a particular ideology and party. This is very common in local election to there were cases of false information about opposition candidate in social media by another candidate in Indian subcontinent recently. Fact checking may take time so by the time the truth uncover it may reach a certain amount of people.[2]

VI. Community Outreach

India's diverse land holds a lot of communities in its heart. Most of them are based on religion, caste, sexual orientation etc. Most of them are underprivileged. Bypassing the barriers of traditional media, social media serves as a megaphone, elevating their views straight to the public and lawmakers. By sharing their own stories, struggles, and demands, these communities may now promote understanding and awareness of topics that were previously taboo. Social media also crosses geographical barriers by creating online communities that enable underprivileged people to interact, find support, and organize for group action. This gives them the ability to plan petitions, campaigns, and demonstrations, which they may use to pressure government officials and bring about change at the local level.[7]

Social media gives underrepresented communities the power to reclaim their proper place in the political sphere by combating invisibility and upending prevailing narratives.

Nonetheless, it's critical to recognize the difficulties presented by false information, online harassment, and echo

Algorithm-driven misinformation and echo chambers have the power to splinter communities and warp reality especially in rural areas where most of them use these mobiles as their form of news. Participation is discouraged by online harassment, particularly for historically underrepresented communities. Filter bubbles prevent people from being exposed to different viewpoints, which obstructs productive discussion and may widen already existing gaps. In the end, how social media affects rural politics will depend on our capacity to manage its intricacies, utilizing its opportunities for accountability and connection while minimizing its risks of discord and false information.

VII. Literature Review

a. Studies conducted in 2012 by Valenzuela et al. and Barberá et al. (2015)[14]

The relevance of social media platforms in promoting political participation and engagement has been emphasized in this study. These studies imply that social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp function as hubs for political discourse, information exchange, and mobilization, boosting citizens' political efficacy and encouraging in-person political engagement

b. Research by Bode and Dalrymple (2016) and Gil de Zúñiga et al. (2014)[3]

This essay has investigated the connection between political efficacy and social media use. Researchers discovered that people who interact with political information on social media platforms typically exhibit higher levels of political efficacy, which includes perceptions of political efficacy and competency as well as confidence in political institutions. These results imply that social media can have a beneficial impact on citizens' beliefs about their capacity to bring about political change.

c. Studies by Brundidge (2010) and Kushin and Kitchener(2009)[4]

The relationship between social media use and offline political activity—such as voting, going to political events, and participating in grassroots activism—has been examined in this essay. There appears to be a positive association between online political participation and offline political activity, since these research imply that those who are active on social media platforms are also more likely to engage in offline political activities.

d. Research by Tripathi (2019) and Chari and Gupta(2018)[12]

This article has looked at how social media affects political mobilization and communication in the context of India. They discovered that political leaders and parties in India have been using social media platforms more frequently to interact with voters, spread political ideas, and rally support, all of which have an impact on political discourse and behaviour

VIII. Methodology

a. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative approach to gather and examine the importance and frequency of the use of social media in the grassroots levels of rural and urban places located in India

b. Data collection

The data collection was conducted through an online questionnaire to a diverse sample of respondents. The questionnaire included demographic questions (age group, gender, local constituency type) and questions related to social media usage and its impact on political engagement

c. Sample

The sample for the study collected from citizens of India living in different socioeconomic situations and in different demographics mainly divided into urban and rural areas.

IX. Data Interpretation

a. Hypothesis 1- relationship between frequency of social media use and change in political views

Fig. 1 Relationship between Opinion Change and Opinion sharing frequency

The study looked at the relationship between social media usage frequency and changes in political opinions, with the null hypothesis predicting no association and the alternative showing otherwise. A significant correlation was discovered using a chi-square test, as indicated by a p-value of 0.0360, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. This means that there is a statistically significant association between how frequently people interact with social media sites and their likelihood of changing their political views. [10]

b. Hypothesis-2: The correlation between frequency of sharing opinions on social media and perception of its reach at the grassroots level.

Fig. 2.1 Relationship between Social Media Reach and Opinion sharing frequency

Fig. 2.2 Scatter Plot of Social Media Reach and Opinion sharing frequency.

The study shows that the relationship between how often people share their thoughts on social media and their perceived reach at the grassroots level. The null hypothesis anticipated no significant link, whereas the alternative suggested otherwise. The Pearson association Coefficient revealed a significant negative association (p-value = 0.0012), resulting to the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. This shows that there is a strong association between how often people pen their thoughts on social media and their perception of its reach at the grassroots level. The negative correlation shows that as people share their thoughts with greater frequency, their perceived reach at the grassroots level decreases.

Hypothesis 3- relationship between belief in social media's role in promoting transparency and accountability and belief in its future effectiveness as a political tool.

Fig. 3 Relationship Between Transparency Promotion and Future Effectiveness

The study looked at the relationship between belief in social media's potential to encourage openness and accountability and belief in its future efficacy as a political tool. The null hypothesis shows there was no meaningful association, but the alternative proposed otherwise. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient revealed a statistically significant negative correlation with a p-value of 0.0172, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.05 significance level. This suggests that there is a significant relationship between these ideas, with a negative correlation implying that as belief in social media's role in fostering transparency and accountability grows, belief in its potential efficacy as a political instrument declines.

Hypothesis 4- the association between gender and experiencing negative impacts of social media on engagement

Fig. 4 Relationship Between Gender and Negative Impacts

The study sought to investigate the link between gender and perceiving negative effects of social media on involvement. The null hypothesis proposed no such association, but the alternative suggested otherwise. Using the chi-square test for independence, the acquired result produced a p-value of 0.0498 and a chi-square statistic of 12.60, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis at a significance level of 0.05. This shows that there is a link between gender and the deciding effects of social media activity.

V. Conclusion

Using the four given hypothesis, this study investigated the complex nature of social media's influence on grassroots politics in India and discovered significant connections and correlations. First, a high link has been shown between frequent use of social media and changes in political opinions, demonstrating social media's powerful influence on political behaviour and thought. Then there appears to be a inconsistency between online activism and real life influence, since there is a large negative link between the frequency with which ideas are shared on social media and perceived local reach. Third, there is a strong negative link, raising concerns about social media's long-term impact on future political performance and belief in the platform's ability to create accountability and transparency. Finally, there is a high link between gender. The perception that social media has determining influence on political involvement emphasizes the significance of gender-sensitive efforts.

These findings emphasize the dual character of social media in India's political scene. While it increases access to political information and empowers vulnerable people, it also raises concerns about misinformation, the perceived ineffectiveness of online action, and gender-specific negative experiences. For effectively reaping the benefits while reducing the risks, regulators, political leaders, and social media platforms must work together to boost digital literacy, encourage critical thinking, and ensure equal information access. These measures will assist to enhance India's democratic structure,

making social media a more powerful and dependable tool for political participation and empowerment.

References

[1]"The 2014 Indian elections on Twitter: A comparison of campaign strategies of political parties"

[2]Aasita Bali, Prathik Desai ,Fake News and Social Media: Indian Perspective(2019)

[3] Research by Bode and Dalrymple (2016) and Gil de Zúñiga et al. (2014)

[4] Studies by Brundidge (2010) and Kushin and Kitchener(2009)

[5] CAA Protests: Why are people opposing the Citizenship Amendment Act?

[6] Chadha, K., & Guha, P. "The Bharatiya Janata Party's Online Campaign and Citizen Involvement in India's 2014 Election". International Journal of Communication

[7] Chari, A., & Gupta, A. (2018). Indian political communication in the digital age: The 2014 Indian General Election and beyond. Routledge

[8] India has second highest number of Internet users after China: Report by IAMAI.
<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/internet/india-has-second-highest-number-of-internet-users-after-china-report/articleshow/71311705.cms?from=mdr>

[9] Rao, S. (2018). "Social Media and Democratization in India: Is Facebook the 'New' Media?". Media Asia

[10] S. C. Gupta V.K. Kapoor, "Fundamentals of Mathematical Statistics", Tenth Edition, Sultan Chand Publications, 2010.

[11] Srirupa Roy, Being the Change: The Aam Aadmi Party and the Politics of the Extraordinary in Indian Democracy

[12] Tripathi, S. (2019). Social media and political communication: Concept, practices and trends. Routledge.

[13] T. K. Bijimol, John T. Abraham, D. Jyothi Ratnam, Machine Translation System for Translation of Malayalam Morphological Causative Constructions into English Periphrastic Causative, Applications in Ubiquitous Computing', Springer Nature Switzerland AG, ISSN 2522-8609 (electronic), ISBN 978-3-030-35280-6 (eBook), DOI 978-3-030-35280-6_11, 2020

[14] Studies conducted in 2012 by Valenzuela et al. and Barberá et al. (2015)

<https://www.weforum.org/publications/global-risks-report-2024/>

[15] The World Economic Forum's 'Global Risks Report 2024' 19th edition